

doi: 10.5281/zenodo.3476394

IN SEARCH OF LOGIC IN TRANSLATION: INDUCTION, DEDUCTION OR ABDUCTION?

У пошуках логіки в перекладі: індукція, дедукція чи абдукція?

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Abstract

The abstract is dealing with experimental research as a means of exposing procedural specifics of translation. Introspective experimental method known as TAP (Think-Aloud Protocol) was initially developed by psychologists but later successfully utilized for the needs of Translation Studies. Within the experiment that involved six semi-professional subjects, their concurrent verbalizations were studied with the purpose of exposing such logical mechanisms of the translator's decision-making as induction, deduction and abduction. The experiment revealed how these mechanisms interact in resolving some typical translation problems like the selection of a translation equivalent on the basis of external (dictionaries) and internal (mental lexicon) sources of information and reproduction of nonequivalent lexical units.

Key words: *Think-Aloud Protocol (TAP), experiment, logic, induction, deduction, abduction.*

Introduction

Psycholinguistics emerged as a synthesis of Linguistics and Psychology aimed at filling the gap between language and speech on the one side and mind and behavior on the other. In its unbridled desire to overcome a potential speculativeness of such an ambitious endeavor, Psycholinguistics from its outset relied heavily on experimental data. Since Linguistics had never been experiment-oriented, Psycholinguistics borrowed some of its techniques from Psychology, which was the case with a method known as Think-Aloud Protocol (or TAP) that turned out ideally suited for investigating psycholinguistic aspects of translation.

Psycholinguistic turn in the study of language coincided with attempts to expose the procedural essence of translation as a form of interlinguistic, interpersonal and intercultural communication. Introducing a process-oriented dimension into Translation Studies (Федоров, 2002) inevitably turned researchers' attention towards experimental methods capable of lifting a lid off a notorious "black box" of the translator's mind (Jones, 2007).

The *aim* of my experiment was to trace down some basic mechanisms of human logic in the translator's decision making process. The experiment involved 6 semi-professional subjects whose task was to translate the text from English into Ukrainian with parallel verbalization of their thoughts (considerations).

Methods and techniques of the research

TAP was derived from the method of "verbal reports on thinking" ascribed to American psychologists Karl Anders Ericsson and Herbert Alexander Simon who gave its theoretical substantiation in a number of their works (Ericsson & Simon, 1980; Ericsson & Simon, 1983; Ericsson, 2003). Some psychologists expressed concern that tasks-completing results obtained through verbalization could be reactive meaning that the performance of participants giving the reports differed from that of silent control subjects. In response to the claims of verbal reports' cognitive inconsistency, Ericsson and Simon developed their *information processing model* whose crucial aspect is that the information contained in the attention of the experiment's subjects remains the same with the verbal report procedure as it would be without it, that is, when the cognitive processes proceed silently. The only observable difference between verbalized and non-verbalized task-completing is that participants would take longer to complete the tasks while thinking aloud – presumably because of the additional time required for completing vocalization of the verbal expression of their thoughts.

The main advantage of TAPs is that they provide an opportunity to obtain some information about the specifics of all the possible stages of translation process, e.g., perceiving information, its interpreting, formation of its mental representation, selection / creation of the means of reproducing the image formed in the translator's mind, etc. Thus, appears a unique chance to carry on a complex analysis of translation cognitive essence.

My attention is focused on the specifics of the translator's decision-making that falls under the general definition of this process as "the ability of humans to choose between competing courses of action based on the relative value of their consequences" (Balleine, 2007: 8159). Traditionally, decision-making is viewed as a combination of intuitive and strategic decisions. And while intuitive decisions can be characterized as fast, easy, and computationally light (known as Type 1 processing), strategic ones, on the contrary, are slow, contemplative, and effortful (known as Type 2 processing) (Kahneman, 2011). Type 1 processing occurs outside of human awareness and is believed to utilize small amounts of working memory. In contrast, Type 2 processing is of a logical nature and thus requires significant working memory and significant need for cognitive control.

Consequently, I assume that introspective experiments such as TAPs cannot principally expose any intuitive decisions, while any recorded considerations concerning the translator's decision-making should be regarded as Type 2 processing of a logical-strategic character.

Results

Since logic is usually defined as a method of cognition based primarily on two mechanisms – *induction* and *deduction* – my major intention was to see if I could find in the subjects' reports any indications of these mechanisms' influence on their decisions.

Induction is commonly recognized as transference from separate facts to general conclusions, while *deduction*, on the contrary, – from general conclusions to separate facts. Since the final result of a decision-making process in translation (almost) never follows from the initial conditions (thesis confirmed by the idea of translation multiplicity), the translators' conclusions are (almost) always incomplete (partial) or probabilistic. It can be supposed that all translators give preference to a deductive way of information processing if we take for deduction looking up for equivalents in the dictionaries which, in this particular case, play the role of linguistic norms, i.e., 'general conclusions' in terms of logic. For more advanced professionals, deductive way of decision-making goes from their mental lexicons to linguistic exteriorizations, i.e., speaking metaphorically, 'external' dictionaries are substituted for 'internal' ones. Hand in hand with expected striving to process mentally a

maximal number of potential variants of translation (which can be treated as a “maze solving” heuristic), extensive use of vocabularies can point at some negative factors like a low level of linguistic and/or translation competence, limited scope of background knowledge on the topic, lack of self-confidence, etc. In particular, in the course of my experiment, Russian-speaking subjects turned to dictionaries in search of Ukrainian equivalents after they’d selected the Russian ones (and often from their mental lexicons only) which considerably hindered their decision-making.

The facts of referring to dictionaries are not always registered in the protocols explicitly but sometimes can be inferred indirectly, like in cases when the translator begins going over potential variants of translation.

Taking into account both direct and indirect cases of dictionary references, I counted them: for TAP # 1 – 41, TAP #2 – 6, TAP # 3 – 46, TAP # 4 – 25, TAP # 5 – 22 and TAP # 6 – 52. The data for TAPs # 1, 3, 4, 5 and 6 may be considered as correlative while the reduction of references for TAP # 2 can be explained by specificity of verbalizing by the subject who gave preference not so much to accounting for his/her actions as to formulating his/her impressions and associations.

Separate inductive reasonings in TAPs are rather exceptions than a rule because generalizations associated with cognitive induction are not revealed in the translator’s concrete decisions but instead accumulated in his/her memory providing the foundation for future decisions. When facing the problem, the translator is employing a “trial-and-error heuristic” to look for a word or expression that fits the context best. Then (s)he generalizes this experience with the help of induction and in future resorts to acquired experience for processing some new material, i.e. begins to act deductively. Thus, it would be more accurate to speak about the joint action of both these mechanisms and, correspondingly, decisions in translation are rather of a complex inductive-deductive nature.

Proceeding from the translator’s reflections, I can construct a cognitive decision-making model for such particular situation as ascribing a meaning to a non-equivalent source lexeme: the absence of a word in the subject’s mental lexicon drives him/her to turn for help to a dictionary (induction), while the analogous absence of a word in a dictionary leads to the attempt(s) to formulate some meaning on the basis of available general information about English morphology and word-formation (deduction).

At the same time, inductive and deductive elements of the translator's logic can be consolidated in the notion of *abduction* put forward and described by Charles Pierce as “the process of forming an explanatory hypothesis” (Bellucci, 2018: 3). Following the line of exposing interactivity among different mechanisms of the translator's logic, we accept the assumption that “abduction is not an isolated form of reasoning, but is embedded within the larger horizon of inquiry, because a hypothesis is first put forth by abduction, and then verified by induction (through verification of its observable deductive consequences)” (Ibid.: 6).

In particular, abduction helps explain the creative nature of the translator's decision-making. If the translator faces difficulties with reproducing the meaning and/or form of (a) certain sign(s), (s)he can resolve this problem by putting forward various hypotheses as to the aspects of translation process in need with their consequent verifying or nullifying and putting forward alternative hypotheses. In my eyes, this activity can be regarded as a cognitive variability peculiar to translation together with linguistic and contextual (situational) ones.

Conclusions

(1) The analysis of the subjects' concurrent verbalizations allowed not only to follow the work of such fundamental logical mechanisms of the translator's decision-making as deduction, induction and abduction, but also to expose how they interact in different problematic situations (such as dealing with non-equivalent lexical units or selecting an equivalent on the basis of external and internal lexicons) and develop corresponding cognitive models of their resolving.

(2) Methodology-wise, my research ones again demonstrates a really pressing need for joint interdisciplinary effort in determining procedural specifics of translation that would unite specialists in the fields of Psychology, Physiology, Neuroscience, etc. Experimental research doesn't only have considerable explanatory potential capable of neutralizing excessive speculativeness of Translation Studies but is also a great educational instrument that helps students cultivate a more conscious approach to translation and contributes to shaping their professional competence.

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